

Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum

Meeting Summary – 18 May 2026

Introduction

The UK Health Data Research Alliance convened its seventh Clinical Trials Stakeholder Prioritisation Forum on 18 May 2026, bringing together stakeholders to discuss challenges and priorities related to the use of health data in clinical trials. The meeting was chaired by Dr Macey Murray (Senior Research Fellow, UCL Innovative Clinical Trials Unit, University College London).

The Forum reiterated its purpose as a cross-stakeholder platform focused on identifying practical challenges and developing actionable solutions, rather than acting purely as a discussion group.

Macey Murray explained that the agenda for the session was informed by a prior survey of members, with a focus on data sharing, particularly onward sharing of data from clinical trials.

Onward Data Sharing in Clinical Trials using Health Systems Data: Three perspectives

Researcher perspective

Mike Robling (Centre for Trials Research, Cardiff University) [presented](#) a session which explored the concept of onward data sharing, including its importance for:

- Supporting reproducibility and transparency in research
- Enabling secondary analysis and new research questions
- Maximising the value of publicly funded trials
- Supporting evidence synthesis, including meta-analyses using individual participant data

Despite its importance, it was noted that actual reuse of trial data remains low, even where policies support sharing.

Key Challenges Identified

Through case study examples and discussion, several practical challenges were highlighted:

1. Governance and contractual complexity

- Uncertainty around data controller roles when sharing across organisations and borders
- Complex contracting arrangements with multiple stakeholders
- Duplication of licensing requirements for the same dataset

2. Consent and legacy issues

- Older trials often lack consent that fully supports onward sharing
- Need to revisit privacy notices and participant information
- Inconsistencies in how legacy consent is interpreted and applied

3. Data identifiability and anonymisation

- Significant effort required to demonstrate whether data is identifiable
- Lack of clarity or consistency across organisations in defining anonymised data

4. Operational burden and resourcing

- Substantial time, cost, and effort required to prepare data for sharing
- Activities often occur retrospectively, without prior planning or funding
- Limited availability of expertise to support the process

5. System fragmentation

- Data held across multiple environments and organisations
- Challenges in moving data between secure environments
- Emerging shift to Trusted Research Environments (TREs), but transition still ongoing

Public Perspectives on Data Sharing

Caroline Brocklehurst and Sarah Chave, public representatives on the Transforming Data for Trials Public Advisory Group highlighted four key areas for consideration:

1. Data Quality and Representation

- Risks of sharing incomplete or poor-quality data
- Concerns around missing data and under-representation of certain groups
- Limited capture of patient-reported outcomes compared to clinical measures

2. Trust and Public Benefit

- Importance of clearly communicating the purpose and benefits of data sharing
- Need to demonstrate real-world value beyond cost efficiency
- Concerns around commercial use and potential misuse of data

3. Data Security

- Requirement for clear, standardised processes to mitigate risks
- Importance of explaining how data is stored, de-identified, and protected
- Role of secure environments in building public confidence

4. Consent and Transparency

- Need for meaningful informed consent, particularly for onward sharing
- Challenges around legacy consent and future-proofing
- Importance of involving the public in shaping consent processes

Data Owners Perspectives on Data Sharing – Discussion

Key Themes

- *Balancing access and protection* – Stakeholders emphasised the difficulty in balancing data accessibility for research with the need to protect patient data securely.
- *Data ownership and custodianship* – Discussion highlighted differing perspectives on whether data is “owned” by patients or co-produced with healthcare systems, with agreement on the importance of responsible stewardship.
- *Commercial considerations* – Concerns were raised about ensuring commercial partners are engaged, while maintaining public trust and ensuring benefits are clearly articulated.
- *International competitiveness* – It was noted that barriers to data access and sharing may contribute to trials being conducted outside the UK, impacting patient access to innovative treatments.

Breakout Discussions

Three breakout groups explored the following questions around improving onward data sharing

- What is the single most impactful change that could be made? (and why)
- Define one specific, realistic action (an easy win or a quick fix)
- How do we build and maintain trust?

Key Outputs

- Need for earlier planning for data sharing within trials, including funding and resourcing
- Importance of clear, accessible consent processes that minimise burden on participants
- Strong support for developing case studies and use cases to demonstrate public benefit
- Recognition of the need for support structures (e.g. HDRS) to facilitate data sharing
- Interest in creating registries or catalogues of successful (and unsuccessful) data sharing examples
- Consideration of accreditation approaches for researchers and environments to build trust

Future Directions

The Forum highlighted several priorities for future work:

- Expanding the case study catalogue to include examples of onward data sharing
- Improving guidance and practical tools to support trialists
- Engaging commercial stakeholders more effectively
- Continuing to strengthen public involvement and communication

Conclusion

The meeting reinforced the importance of onward sharing of patient data as part of a trial as a key enabler of impactful clinical research, while also highlighting significant operational, governance, and trust-related challenges.

There was strong agreement that progress will depend on:

- Clearer processes and frameworks
- Better integration of data sharing into trial design
- Strong public engagement
- Practical support and infrastructure

The Forum will continue to focus on producing actionable outputs and solutions to address these challenges

The next meeting was confirmed for 5 November 2026 2.00pm - 3.30pm

Appendix

Contributing Organisation
Cardiff University
Health Research Authority
NHS England
Optimum Patient Care
Our Future Health
Transforming Data for Trials Public Advisory Group
UK Health Data Research Alliance
University College London (UCL)
University of Dundee
University of Oxford
University of Southampton